

science and policy
for a healthy future

Form:

Shipping Category B Biological Substances

Valid since: **October 2017**

Version: **V 1.0**

8.2 ANNEX 2

Shipping Category B Biological Substances

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

Info: Email: HBM4EU@uba.de
Developed by: IBMT, KI, ISCIII, JSI

Shipping Category B Biological Substances

Note: All those who ship Category B Biological Substances and/or Dry Ice must be trained.

Packaging

Leakproof/siftproof primary receptacle	Absorbent	Leakproof/siftproof secondary packaging		Rigid outer packaging
<p>Either your primary or secondary receptacle must be able to withstand internal pressure of 95kPA between -40°C to 55°C without leakage.</p> <p>Limit: For liquid specimens, the primary receptacle must not contain more than 1 L. For dried specimens, the primary receptacle must not exceed the outer packaging weight limit.</p>	<p>For liquids, add enough absorbent to the primary containers to absorb the entire contents of all primary receptacles.</p> <p>Acceptable absorbent materials include cellulose wadding, cotton balls, super-absorbent packets and paper towels.</p>	<p>Use a secondary container that is leakproof for liquid specimens or siftproof for dried specimens. Choose only secondary containers certified by the manufacturer for Biological Substance, Category B (UN 3373) prior to use.</p> <p>To prevent contact between multiple fragile primary receptacles, individually wrap or separate (e.g. Cryobox) them inside the secondary container.</p> <p>Place primary receptacles into leakproof secondary packaging such as container or sealed plastic bags which are compatible with dry ice (-80 ° C) in case of frozen shipments.</p>	<p>If frozen or refrigerated shipment, place your secondary receptacle in an appropriate styrofoam box, place dry ice/ refrigerant packs outside of secondary packaging.</p> <p>If a shipment includes dry ice the outer packaging must allow for the release of carbon dioxide gas when the solid sublimates.</p>	<p>Use rigid outer packaging appropriately sized for the contents.</p> <p>Must allow carbon dioxide gas to vent if shipped with dry ice.</p> <p>Limit the total volume for liquid samples to 4 L and the total weight of dried samples to 4 kg per outer container.</p> <p>Before sealing the outer packaging, you must make an itemized list of the contents of the package and enclose the list together with the completed transfer protocol between the secondary packaging and outer packaging.</p>

Labeling and Marking on outer Package

	Required Information	Required only if packaged with dry ice	Required only if > 50 ml liquid in primary container, place two labels on opposite sites	Correct marked and labeled package Category B on dry ice

Sample shipment from EU countries to non-EU countries

Additionally to the Sample Transfer Protocol, the List of Content, and the air waybill a **pro-forma invoice** is required. For customs clearance, **attach the original of the pro-forma invoice and two copies in a protective bag to the outside of the overpack**. As pro-forma invoice use the attached template HBM4EU_WP7.4_Pro-Forma Invoice_V1.0.docx.

Further county specific import permits might be required. **The receiver has to provide the permit to the shipper**. It should be placed jointly with the pro-forma invoice in the protective bag outside the box.

